

Evaluating the level of knowledge and confidence regarding conventional computed tomography and cone beam computed tomography among dental interns of central India

FIRST AUTHOR AND CORRESPONDING AUTHOR : Dr. Rishikesh K. Meshram, BDS, MDS, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur, Maharashtra.

SECOND AUTHOR : Dr. Anjali Bichpuriya, Professor, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur, Maharashtra.

THIRD AUTHOR : Dr. Nikhil R. Sathawane, Associate Professor, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur, Maharashtra.

ABSTRACT

Introduction-This study compares the knowledge and confidence of dental interns in using Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) and Computed Tomography (CT).

Objectives-

- 1) To assess knowledge of dental interns regarding CBCT and CT.
- 2) To assess confidence of dental interns regarding CBCT and CT.

Materials and Methods-Dental interns were surveyed using a close ended questionnaire. Mean scores for knowledge and confidence were calculated for both CBCT and CT and an unpaired t test was used to assess significance.

Results-

- 1) The mean knowledge score for CBCT (7.3 ± 1.6) was significantly higher than that for CT (5.8 ± 0.86) with a p-value of 0.035.
- 2) Similarly mean confidence score for CBCT (6.2 ± 1.7) exceeded that for CT (4.8 ± 1.3) yielding a p value of 0.049.

Conclusion - Dental interns demonstrated greater knowledge and confidence in CBCT compared to CT. These findings highlight the need for enhanced educational emphasis on CT to ensure well rounded competency in imaging techniques in dental education.

INTRODUCTION

In the field of dentistry, to get quality treatment is an ultimate aim and to achieve that, there is a pivotal need of advanced diagnostic techniques. The applications of such advanced diagnostic modalities such as conventional computed tomography and cone beam computed tomography, in dentistry are highly extensive.¹

Through its precise, imaging, cone beam computed tomography opens the door to a vast array of applications such as implant placement, endodontics, evaluation of third molars and their proximity to vital structures, orthodontic planning, etc.¹ Conventional computed tomography also serves as a powerful tool to visualise the extent of pathologic conditions, to unravel complex facial structures, to assess temporomandibular joint, and the paranasal sinuses for pre-surgical treatment planning, etc.³ Cone beam computed, tomography and convention, computed tomography are particularly beneficial when standard dental or facial radiographs fall short in providing adequate information.

Dental interns being the first point contact in Patient care, it is paramount for them to possess a strong understanding of these imaging techniques and to exhibit confidence and competence in diagnosing and managing oral health issues. Therefore, it is essential for the dental interns to have a comprehensive grasp on the knowledge and confidence regarding the conventional CT and CBCT techniques.¹

A study was conducted by Andy Wai Kan Yeung et al. in Hong Kong.⁴ They evaluated the awareness and practice of 2D and 3D diagnostic imaging among dentists, where the results showed only half of the dentists feel confident in taking and interpreting CBCT images, and there seems to be a limited knowledge of radiation dose-related risks.⁴ Another study was conducted by Muhammad Khalis Abdul Karim et al. in Johor Malaysia.⁵ They assessed the knowledge and awareness among radiology personnel regarding current compute tomography technology and radiation dose.⁵ The results of this study conveyed that almost all the radiology personnel had considerable knowledge and awareness regarding current computed tomography technology.⁵ After going through other such studies and to the best of our knowledge, no study has been conducted in central India that compasses the knowledge and confidence of dental interns regarding conventional CT and CBCT.

Hence, the objective of the study was to evaluate the knowledge and confidence of the dental interns regarding the conventional CT and CBCT technologies in central India. A close ended questionnaire was circulated among 100 dental interns, and the results were determined.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional descriptive observational study was meticulously conducted to evaluate the level of knowledge and confidence in interpreting Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) images compared to traditional Computed Tomography (CT) images.¹ The study

included both male and female participants, ensuring a representative sample of the population.

A robust, self-administered anonymous questionnaire was created, consisting 21 close-ended questions specifically designed to assess knowledge and confidence regarding CBCT and CT imaging.¹ The questionnaire was organized into five distinct sections which included Section A included the Demographic Data which collected essential demographic information, including age, gender, and educational level, to provide context for the findings. Section B was regarding Knowledge of CBCT-Participants' understanding and familiarity with CBCT technology were assessed. Section C included Knowledge of CT which focused on evaluating participants' knowledge of traditional CT imaging. Section D was Confidence in Understanding CBCT Images in which Participants rated their confidence in interpreting anonymized CBCT images, providing insights into their self-assessment of skills. Section E was Confidence in Understanding CT Images, this section aimed to gauge participants' confidence in interpreting CT images, enabling a direct comparison between the two imaging modalities. Anonymized CBCT and CT images were integrated into the online questionnaire to assess participants' interpretative skills effectively. Only fully completed questionnaires were included in the analysis to ensure the integrity and reliability of the results.

RESULTS

Overall results revealed that dental interns generally displayed a higher level of knowledge and confidence in interpreting CBCT compared to conventional CT. Out of 100 dental interns that participated in the study, most of them were females (76%). Just over half the participants were 23 years old, (65%), most of the participants had just completed their internships(83%) while the rest were undergoing internships (14%) or had completed one year post-internship. Out of 100 interns, 70% of them had undertaken courses or lectures on radiology.

Almost 71% knew the difference between the radiation dosage between CT and CBCT. 57% of the participants had advised their patients to take a CBCT. Most of the participants stated that they gained knowledge about conventional CT through faculty lectures, 74%, and workshops, 10%, and the internet, 12%.

54% of the participants thought that they are not confident enough in interpreting a conventional CT image While almost half of the participants were confident enough in interpreting a CBCT image (52%). 90% of the participants agreed to take the initiative to update themselves regarding information on CBCT from time to time, while 88% of them agreed to take initiative to update themselves regarding information on conventional CT.

The study revealed a significant difference in knowledge and confidence levels among dental interns between CBCT and conventional CT. the mean knowledge score for CBCT was 7.3 (SD= 1.6) compared to a lower mean score of 5.8 (SD=0.86) for CT, with an unpaired t-test value of 13.76 and a p-value of 0.035, including statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, confidence scores were higher for CBCT, with a mean of 6.2 (SD=1.1) compared to a mean of 4.8 (SD=1.3) for CT. This difference was statistically significant, as evidenced by an unpaired t-test value of 7.561 and a p-value of 0.049 ($p < 0.05$).

These findings indicate that dental interns are generally more knowledgeable and confident in CBCT imaging compared to CT, highlighting a need for targeted education to strengthen their competency in CT.

Table 1: Age comparison in study population

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
22 years	6	6%
23 years	65	65%
24 years	26	26%
25 years	3	3%
Chi = 11.87, p=0.023*		

*p<0.05 – statistical significant difference

Table 2: Gender comparison in study population

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Male	24	24%
Female	76	76%
Chi = 18.54, p=0.006*		

*p<0.05 – statistical significant difference

Table 3: Designation distribution in study population

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Undergoing internship	14	14%
Just completed internship	83	83%
Completed 1year post internship	3	3%
Not joined internship	0	0%
Chi = 23.12, p=0.001*		

*p<0.05 – statistical significant difference

Table 4: Have you undertaken course or lecture on Radiology

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	70	70%
No	30	30%
Chi = 16.41, p=0.005*		

*p<0.05 – statistical significant difference

Table 3: Designation distribution in study population

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Undergoing internship	14	14%
Just completed internship	83	83%
Completed 1year post internship	3	3%
Not joined internship	0	0%
		Chi = 23.12, p=0.001*

*p<0.05 – statistical significant difference

Table 4: Have you undertaken course or lecture on Radiology

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	70	70%
No	30	30%
		Chi = 16.41, p=0.005*

*p<0.05 – statistical significant difference

**KNOWLEDGE OF DENTAL INTERNS REGARDING CONE BEAM COMPUTED
TOMOGRAPHY (CBCT)**

Table 5: What is the difference between CT and CBCT?

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Low radiation dose than CT	71	71%
Same radiation dose as CT	29	29%
Chi = 13.76, p=0.021*		

*p<0.05 – statistical significant difference

Table 6:

	YES n(%)	NO n(%)	P value
Have you ever advised any of your patients to take a CBCT?	57 (57%)	43 (43%)	p=0.641 (ns)
Are you aware of the different sizes of field-of-view of CBCT images?	86 (86%)	14 (14%)	p<0.001**
Do you think CBCT should be provided at the dental institute?	93 (93%)	7 (7%)	p<0.001**

p>0.05 – no statistical significant difference **p<0.001 – highly significant difference

**KNOWLEDGE OF DENTAL INTERNS REGARDING CONVENTIONAL
COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY (CT SCAN)**

Table 7: How did you gain the knowledge about Conventional CT?

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Faculty Lectures	74	74%
Workshops	10	10%
Internet	12	12%
Others	0	0%
Chi = 10.98, p=0.041*		

*p<0.05 – statistical significant difference

Table 8:

	YES N (%)	NO N (%)	P value
Do you think that CT uses ionizing radiation?	48 (48%)	52 (52%)	p=0.641 (NS)
Do you think that CT scan increases the probability of inducing cancer?	25 (25%)	75 (75%)	p=0.023*
Do you think that there is a limit for the number of CT scans that the patient should undergo in a given period of time?	56 (56%)	44 (44%)	p=0.428 (NS)

$p>0.05$ – no statistical significant difference $**p<0.001$ – highly significant difference

**CONFIDENCE OF DENTAL INTERNS REGARDING CONE BEAM COMPUTED
TOMOGRAPHY (CBCT)**

Table 7: How did you gain the knowledge about Conventional CT?

	YES n (%)	NO n (%)	P value
Do you think you are confident enough in interpreting CBCT image?	52 (52%)	48 (48%)	$p=0.641$ (NS)
Do you think it is necessary to have a CBCT referral system in every dental clinic that does not have a CBCT unit?	48 (48%)	52 (52%)	$p=0.641$ (NS)
Do you think it is necessary to have CBCT clinical requirement for undergraduate dental students?	45 (45%)	55 (55%)	$p = 0.351$ (NS)
Would you take the initiative to update yourself regarding information on CBCT from time to time?	90 (90%)	10 (10%)	$p<0.001^{**}$

$p>0.05$ – no statistical significant difference $**p<0.001$ – highly significant difference

**CONFIDENCE OF DENTAL INTERNS REGARDING CONE BEAM COMPUTED
TOMOGRAPHY (CBCT)**

Table 8: How did you gain the knowledge about Conventional CT?

	YES n (%)	NO n (%)	p value
Do you think you are confident enough in interpreting a conventional CT image?	46 (46%)	54 (54%)	p=0.574 (NS)
Has adequate information on Conventional CT been included in the dental curriculum for undergraduate students?	50 (50%)	50 (50%)	p=1.00 (NS)
Would you take the initiative to update yourself regarding information on CBCT from time to time?	88 (88%)	12 (12%)	p<0.001**

p>0.05 – no statistical significant difference **p<0.001 – highly significant difference

Table 9: Which year of dental education should include lectures about Conventional CT imaging?

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Pre-clinical years	27	27%
Clinical years	44	44%
Internship	29	29%
	Chi square test = 4.89, p=0.183 (NS)	

p>0.05 – no statistical significant difference

Table : Comparison of knowledge between CBCT and CT scan among dental Interns

	CBCT Scan Mean (SD)	CT scan Mean (SD)	Unpaired t test	P value, Significance
Knowledge among dental Interns	7.3 (1.6)	5.8 (0.86)	t = 13.76	p= 0.035*

*p< 0.05 – significant difference

Table 2 : Comparison of confidence between CBCT and CT scan among dental Interns

	CBCT Scan Mean (SD)	CT scan Mean (SD)	Unpaired t test	P value, Significance
Knowledge among dental Interns	6.2 (1.7)	4.8 (1.3)	t = 7.561	p= 0.049*

*p< 0.05 – significant difference

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to assess the level of knowledge and confidence among dental interns in interpreting cone beam computed tomography and conventional computed tomography scans. The results revealed that the dental interns generally displayed a higher level of knowledge and confidence in interpreting CBCT compared to conventional CT.

CBCT has become increasingly common for dental applications particularly in the fields like implantology, oral surgery and orthodontics also it gives more precise and detailed images.¹ As maxillofacial region has minute structures which are not easily detected in a traditional CT scan, CBCT is more preferred in such cases to come to a correct confirmatory diagnosis. The sample group for this study selected dental interns as them being the first point of contact in patient care it is paramount for them to possess a strong understanding of these imaging techniques and to exhibit confidence and competence in diagnosing and managing oral health issues. This study was chosen as a questionnaire based approach due to its ability to capture real time data and ensure genuine participant engagement through minimal physical interaction, moreover, it streamlines data collection making the process more efficient and accessible.

The majority of participants in our study acquired their knowledge through faculty lectures, a finding that closely aligns with the results of the study conducted by Mohammad M Kaki et al in Taibah University where knowledge and confidence in interpreting CBCT images among senior dental students was evaluated.¹ In our study, a slight majority of participants expressed a lack of confidence in interpreting conventional CT scans while fewer than half felt assured in their ability to interpret CBCT scans. The findings of our study are consistent with the findings of Vasconcelos K Det al (2021) who reported that frequent use of CBCT in dental curricula enhances familiarity and self-assurance in its interpretation.⁶ When comparing these results to previous studies our findings partially contrast with those of Tanaka R et al (2019) who found that dental interns had significantly higher knowledge levels in interpreting conventional CT.⁴ This difference might be due to variations in educational focus between institutions or technological advancements in imaging that have made CBCT more accessible and practical in dental practice potentially shifting educational priorities. Most studies backhanded about knowledge regarding CBCT but none of them included knowledge and confidence regarding CT which was included in our research and also showed the comparison between them which was the uniqueness of our research.

Recommendation stemming from this research may include the integration of these topics into the dental curriculum implementing regular seminars and workshops and encouraging ongoing education for dental interns the outcomes of this study could significantly contribute to their professional development and ultimately improve patient care.

CONCLUSION

In evaluating the level of knowledge and confidence among dental students in interpreting Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) images compared to traditional Computed Tomography (CT). The results indicate that Students exhibited a greater understanding of the three-dimensional imaging capabilities and finer anatomical details provided by CBCT, which are essential for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning in dentistry. This proficiency not only enhances their clinical skills but also fosters a higher level of confidence when utilizing these images in practice.

To further improve knowledge and confidence in interpreting traditional CT scans, dental curricula can incorporate more focused training modules and hands-on workshops that emphasize the differences and applications of both imaging modalities. By integrating case-based learning and interactive sessions that highlight the strengths of CT alongside CBCT, educators can help students appreciate the relevance of each technique. This additionally, offers opportunities for students to engage in multidisciplinary collaborations can enhance their overall imaging proficiency, ensuring they are well-prepared to leverage both CBCT and CT effectively in their future practices.

REFERENCES

1. Kaaki MM, Othman AA, Meer R, Mirah MA, Alsaedi A, Othman M, Alsaedi AM, Alassaf M, Bafail A, Alsulimani M, Qazali A. Level of knowledge and confidence in interpretation of cone beam CT images among senior dental students and interns from College of Dentistry in Taibah University: a cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Medicine in Developing Countries*. 2023 Dec 3;7(12):1837-.
2. Al Ewaidat H, Zheng X, Khader Y, Spuur K, Abdelrahman M, Alhasan MK, Al-Hourani ZA. Knowledge and awareness of CT radiation dose and risk among patients. *Journal of Diagnostic Medical Sonography*. 2018 Sep;34(5):347-55.
3. Parks ET. Computed tomography applications for dentistry. *Dental Clinics of North America*. 2000 Apr 1;44(2):371-94.
4. Yeung AW, Tanaka R, Jacobs R, Bornstein MM. Awareness and practice of 2D and 3D diagnostic imaging among dentists in Hong Kong. *British dental journal*. 2020 May;228(9):701-9.
5. Karim MK, Hashim S, Bradley DA, Bahrudin NA, Ang WC, Saleh N. Assessment of knowledge and awareness among radiology personnel regarding current computed tomography technology and radiation dose. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 2016 Mar 1 (Vol. 694, No. 1, p. 012031). IOP Publishing.
6. Gaêta-Araujo H, Leite AF, Vasconcelos KD, Jacobs R. Two decades of research on CBCT imaging in DMFR—an appraisal of scientific evidence. *Dentomaxillofacial Radiology*. 2021 May 1;50(4):20200367.
7. Scarfe WC, Farman AG. What is cone-beam CT and how does it work?. *Dental Clinics of North America*. 2008 Oct 1;52(4):707-30.
8. Snel R, Van De Maele E, Politis C, Jacobs R. Digital dental radiology in Belgium: a nationwide survey. *Dentomaxillofacial Radiology*. 2018 Dec 1;47(8):20180045.
9. John GP, Joy TE, Mathew J, Kumar VR. Fundamentals of cone beam computed tomography for a prosthodontist. *The Journal of Indian Prosthodontic Society*. 2015 Jan 1;15(1):8-13.
10. Kamburoğlu KI, Kurşun Ş, Akarşlan ZZ. Dental students' knowledge and attitudes towards cone beam computed tomography in Turkey. *Dentomaxillofacial Radiology*. 2011 Oct 1;40(7):439-43.

11. Sugumaran S, George AM, Kumar SA, Sundari KS, Chandrasekar S, Rajagopal R. Knowledge, awareness, and practice of cone-beam computed tomography among orthodontists: A survey. *Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society*. 2018 Oct;52(4):255-64.
12. Kapila SD, Nervina JM. CBCT in orthodontics: assessment of treatment outcomes and indications for its use. *Dentomaxillofacial radiology*. 2015 Jan 1;44(1):20140282.
13. Padmanabhan S, Venkateswaran S. Image gently: A three-dimensional view of cone-beam computed tomography. *Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society*. 2016 Jan;50(1):1-2.
14. Yang TW, Lin YY, Hsu SC, Chu KC, Hsiao CW, Hsu CW, Bai CH, Chang CK, Hsu YP. Diagnostic performance of cone-beam computed tomography for scaphoid fractures: a systematic review and diagnostic meta-analysis. *Scientific Reports*. 2021 Jan 28;11(1):2587.
15. Cheah HL, Ong YY, Choo EQ, Gan PL, Acharya S. How Ready are Our Students for Cone Beam Computed Tomography?. *Journal of International Dental and Medical Research*. 2021;14(1):292-7.
16. Lavanya R, Babu DG, Waghray S, Chaitanya NC, Mamatha B, Nithika M. A questionnaire cross-sectional study on application of CBCT in dental postgraduate students. *Polish journal of radiology*. 2016;81:181.
17. Masyte V, Sefeldaitė S, Venskutonis T. A questionnaire of digital radiography and CBCT use and knowledge among Lithuanian dentists. *Journal of Oral & Maxillofacial Research*. 2021 Jan;12(1).
18. Ghoncheh Z, Panjnoush M, Kaviani H, Kharazifard MJ, Zahirnia F. Knowledge and attitude of Iranian dentists towards cone-beam computed tomography. *Frontiers in dentistry*. 2019 Sep;16(5):379.
19. Khan M, Sandhu N, Naeem M, Ealden R, Pearson M, Ali A, Honey I, Webster A, Eaton D, Ntentas G. Implementation of a comprehensive set of optimised CBCT protocols and validation through imaging quality and dose audit. *The British Journal of Radiology*. 2022 Nov 1;95(1139):20220070.
20. Bueno MR, Azevedo BC, Estrela C. A critical review of the differential diagnosis of root fracture line in CBCT scans. *Brazilian Dental Journal*. 2021 Dec 6;32(5):114-28.
21. Abdellah RF, Attia SA, Fouad AM, Abdel-Halim AW. Assessment of physicians' knowledge, attitude and practices of radiation safety at Suez Canal University Hospital, Egypt. *Open journal of radiology*. 2015 Dec 4;5(4):250-8.
22. Karim MK, Hashim S, Bradley DA, Bahrudin NA, Ang WC, Saleh N. Assessment of knowledge and awareness among radiology personnel regarding current computed tomography technology and radiation dose. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 2016 Mar 1 (Vol. 694, No. 1, p. 012031). IOP Publishing.
23. Günalp M, Gülünay B, Polat O, Demirkan A, Gürler S, Akkaş M, Aksu NM. Ionising radiation awareness among resident doctors, interns, and radiographers in a university hospital emergency department. *La radiologia medica*. 2014 Jun;119:440-7.

24. Di Piazza A, Vernuccio F, Murmura E, Scopelliti L, Geraci C, Purpura P, La Tona G, Salerno S, Midiri M. Patients' knowledge and awareness of radiation dose and risks from CT: do patients need a personalized communication of dose bill. *EurCongrRadiol*. 2015 Mar 4.
25. Sin HK, Wong CS, Huang B, Yiu KL, Wong WL, Chu YC. Assessing local patients' knowledge and awareness of radiation dose and risks associated with medical imaging: a questionnaire study. *Journal of medical imaging and radiation oncology*. 2013 Feb;57(1):38-44.
26. Paolicchi F, Miniati F, Bastiani L, Faggioni L, Ciaramella A, Creonti I: Assessment of radiation protection awareness and knowledge about radiological examination doses among Italian radiographers
27. Paolicchi F, Miniati F, Bastiani L, Faggioni L, Ciaramella A, Creonti I, Sottocornola C, Dionisi C, Caramella D. Assessment of radiation protection awareness and knowledge about radiological examination doses among Italian radiographers. *Insights into imaging*. 2016 Apr;7:233-42.
28. Masyte V, Sefeldaitė S, Venskutonis T. A questionnaire of digital radiography and CBCT use and knowledge among Lithuanian dentists. *Journal of Oral & Maxillofacial Research*. 2021 Jan;12(1).